

A Knowledge Graph-Driven Interactive 3D Simulation for Craft Training

Alexandros Makris¹, Ioanna Demeridou¹, Panagiotis Koutlemanis¹, Anastasios Roussos¹, Nikolaos Partarakis^{1,2} and Xenophon Zabulis¹

¹ Institute of Computer Science, Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas (ICS-FORTH), N. Plastira 100, Vassilika Vouton, 70013 Heraklion, Greece
amakris@ics.forth.gr, idemer@ics.forth.gr, koutle@ics.forth.gr,
trossos@ics.forth.gr, partarak@ics.forth.gr,
zabulis@ics.forth.gr

² University of Macedonia, Departments of Applied Informatics (UoM-DAI), 156 Egnatia Street, GR-546 36 Thessaloniki, Greece
partarakis@uom.edu.gr

Abstract. The proposed work presents a new approach to craft education that combines semantic knowledge graphs (KGs) with real-time 3D interactive simulations using the Finite Element Method (FEM). Crafting processes are modelled as KGs, outlining each procedural step, possible errors, and their consequences. Learners practise tasks in a virtual environment where their actions are checked against the KG, enabling real-time feedback and correction. After each task, the workpiece is rendered with physically based visualisation to show realistic outcomes. This method enhances learning by providing predictive guidance, error correction, and high-quality visual feedback.

Keywords: knowledge graphs, finite element method, craft training.

1. Introduction

Craft education demands hands-on practice for skill mastery. Novices often make errors, hindering learning. We propose a new method: integrating semantic knowledge graphs (KG) with real-time 3D FEM simulations. This approach semantically maps crafting processes in KGs, detailing steps, deviations, and impacts. KG nodes represent distinct process steps, explicitly showing correct actions and predictable, correctable, or irreversible errors.

Our interactive simulation environment utilises this semantic representation, enabling learners to engage in realistic, real-time virtual practice. During interaction, the training environment is instantiated based on the KG. This includes selecting the appropriate tools and materials and initialising the workspace where the action will be exercised. Moreover, recorded enactments of the action from the KG provide action execution exemplars.

Upon completing each task, the virtual workpiece is rendered using physically based techniques, which simulate real-world material appearance through light transport simulation. This high-quality visual feedback reinforces learning outcomes by enabling learners to assess the tangible consequences of their procedural decisions.

The proposed method demonstrates how semantic KGs can effectively underpin an educationally powerful simulation environment, enhancing craft education through predictive interaction, real-time corrective guidance, and realistic visualisation.

Mastering craft techniques often requires extensive hands-on practice, during which inexperienced learners typically encounter predictable procedural errors. To facilitate learning, we propose integrating a semantically structured representation of crafting processes with interactive simulations employing FEM-based physics modelling.

Our method proceeds through the following logically interconnected steps:

1. **Semantic Representation of Craft Processes:** A detailed KG encoding the procedural flowchart of the crafting process. Each node in the graph corresponds to specific actions or decision points, enriched with semantic descriptions of process steps, conditions, and potential outcomes.
2. **Real-time Interactive FEM Simulation:** The KG informs a real-time 3D simulation powered by an efficient FEM solver. Learners interact virtually with the simulated tool and workpiece, enabling practice of specific process steps while receiving real-time feedback based on the anticipated procedural pitfalls.
3. **High-Fidelity Rendering for Outcome Assessment:** A physically based renderer realistically depicts the resulting workpiece. This visualisation reinforces the learner's understanding by vividly illustrating the impact of correct or incorrect procedural choices.

The proposed approach integrates educational techniques in crafts, combining semantic knowledge representation with interactive physical simulation. KGs are central in orchestrating the dynamic, predictive, and interactive learning experiences.

2. Related Work

2.1 Knowledge Graphs in Education

Domain-specific KGs are important for understanding specialised fields. [1] stresses that KGs are knowledge representations for personalised learning, curriculum design, and content recommendations. In [2], application-specific KGs are reviewed in educational contexts. [3] studies knowledge mapping for KG development.

2.2 Knowledge Graphs in Learning Crafting Skills

Source [4] investigates knowledge management and transfer within arts and crafts organisations. Handmade products rely on tacit knowledge, yet transfer methods lack standardisation. Improved codification, training, and dedicated repositories are crucial for preserving this knowledge. The construction of KGs using textual sources was proposed in [2]; however, this is insufficient for crafting education, where tacit knowledge and materiality require visual and physically informed learning sources.

Source [5] describes a methodology for using KGs to document and preserve crafts using a dedicated ontology [6], extending the CIDOC CRM, and implemented online. This methodology uses semantic annotation to formalise craft concepts, linking knowledge to multimodal resources. It documents crafting entities: tools, materials, and movements. [7] extends this work by integrating ethnographic observations on

crafting actions, products, tools, and materials. The representation links recordings to nominal and verbal descriptions, enabling inference, external links, and enrichment.

Source [8] underscores the importance of well-structured and organised content to craft eLearning, advocating that organising complex crafting processes in a KG ensures logical flow and meaningful connections between learning elements. [9] emphasises the need for systematic, quantitative evaluation of 3D human movement using ground truth data, in real-world scenarios for traditional crafts.

2.3 Physics-Based Simulation and Interactive Training

Physics-based simulation, at the intersection of computer science and physics, uses numerical methods to approximate physical systems governed by fundamental laws like thermodynamics. FEMs are widely used for simulating deformable solids, fluids, and multi-phase interactions. Recent advances use GPU acceleration, allowing the coupling of mechanical and thermal events.

Real-time simulation and training environments exhibit high utility in training environments. Replicating complex systems and scenarios with increasing fidelity and interactivity offers advantages for training across diverse disciplines [10–14].

The importance and applications of real-time simulation and training environments are increasing. A central theme is to replicate complex real-world scenarios for training [15, 16]. Key aspects include the need for realism and the integration of immersive technologies. Simulating realistic physical behaviour involves complex phenomena such as bending, cutting, or tearing of materials, enhances immersion and training effectiveness and is a key challenge for enhancing realism [17].

2.4 Physically Based Rendering in Educational Contexts

Physics-based simulation is crucial in computer graphics for photorealistic animation of cloth, hair, translucent and shiny objects. Computational methods for modelling and simulating traditional crafts safeguard crafting skills. The framework proposed in [18] simulates crafting actions using the FEM. Actions are classified into forming, subtractive, and additive based on their mechanics. In [19], their visualisation for documentation is demonstrated, using light transport simulation to cope with challenging materials such as transparent and metallic.

In [20], an interactive model and simulation system address craft preservation using virtual reality. The system implementation creates a knowledge base of materials, tools, and processes, enabling interactive simulation for training. The digital model supports and enhances traditional craft training compared to purely physical methods.

3. Methodology

3.1 Crafting Process Representation

The crafting process is represented as a Knowledge Graph (KG) based on an ontology. A process schema, derived from ethnographic studies and authored by ethnographers and information scientists, outlines foreseen temporal, causal, or conditional relationships, action sequences, and decision-based divergences. This

schema is a graph where nodes are steps and edges define relationships. Errors and corrective actions are modelled as branches. Visualised in UML, the graph shows step inputs and outputs. Enacting this schema generates a process, comprising physical interventions, observations, and judgments, all characterised as actions.

Each node references the (a) tools and workpieces employed, (b) their material properties, (c) requisite conditions, and (d) a set of associations between action execution parameters and action outcomes. The knowledge elements in (a), (b), and (c) are described geometrically and physically, as well as the execution parameters in (d). The action outcomes in (d) are the states of the affected entities during and after the action, encoded as FEM volumetric mesh animations.

These knowledge elements are represented physically and semantically. Physical properties and parameters are numerical, and their values are in the SI system. These are the values of geometrical and material properties over time. Objects and actions are knowledge elements registered to a knowledge structure used as a lexicon. Each elementary representation contains a link to its thesauric entry and its recording; 3D for objects and 4D for actions.

3.2 Craft Process Modelling

In modelling traditional craft processes, it is essential to distinguish between the physical entities involved, the actions performed, the agents responsible, and the underlying procedural knowledge that guides activity. The CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC-CRM) offers a rich semantic framework for expressing these distinctions. We use the CRM as described in Table 1.

Workpieces and Products. Our model represents workpieces, the fundamental entities that transform within the crafting process. Regardless of whether a workpiece originates as raw, unprocessed material or emerges as the refined output of a preceding production stage, it is consistently represented as an instance of the CIDOC-CRM entity 'E18 Physical Thing'. This classification is deliberately broad, encompassing any tangible item characterised by a persistent physical identity that renders it capable of being subject to the operations in a crafting process.

The designation as E18 ensures that workpieces, irrespective of their origin or stage of completion, are uniformly treated as individual physical entities. This allows for tracking and management of these items throughout their represented processes.

Our model introduces a more specific classification for workpieces that result from intentional human activity in manufacturing. Such workpieces, embodying the tangible outcome of earlier production efforts, are additionally categorised as an instance of 'E24 Physical Man-Made Thing'.

This distinction between E18 and E24 serves a central purpose. It provides a mechanism for tracing the evolving status and provenance of physical objects as they progress through successive phases of transformation. By identifying workpieces that are products of prior manufacturing steps, we maintain a history of their treatment. This is essential for provenance tracking, quality control, and the understanding of manufacturing processes involving multiple stages. The dual classification allows capturing the physical workpiece nature and its status as a product.

Table 1. CIDOC CRM-Based Ontological Mapping of Craft Concepts.

CRM Class	Concept	Description in CRM Context	Role in Craft Model
E18 Physical Thing	Material or workpiece	Any persistent item with a physical identity.	Represents all workpieces, whether raw or already transformed.
E24 Physical Man-Made Thing	Product of the previous step	A physical object intentionally created or modified by humans; subclass of E18.	Used for products of previous steps in the crafting process.
E5 Event	General Event	Any phenomenon occurring over time.	Superclass of E7, used to model the general event structure of processes.
E7 Activity	Actions	A deliberate action performed by an actor to achieve a goal, with a start and end time.	Represents individual craft actions, such as shaping or hammering.
E52 Time-Span	Temporal context	A defined period with a beginning and an end.	Specifies when a crafting action takes place.
E53 Place	Spatial context	A location in which something occurred or existed.	Specifies where the action is performed.
E39 Actor	Practitioner	A person or group that performs activities or bears responsibility.	Represents the craft practitioner or team responsible for the action.
E29 Design or Procedure	Process schema	A plan, workflow, or design describing how something should be done.	Encodes idealised process structures including steps, decisions, and error handling.

The selection of CIDOC CRM as the ontological foundation is motivated by its status as a widely adopted standard in the cultural heritage domain, particularly in terms of the semantic interoperability and long-term sustainability of the data. Unlike lightweight schema languages (e.g., JSON-LD-based custom vocabularies) or task-specific ontologies (e.g., OWL ontologies for manufacturing workflows), CIDOC CRM provides a rich and extensible conceptual framework that distinguishes between activities, actors, places, and designed procedures. This makes it suitable for representing craft processes that combine material transformations with cultural and social context. While alternative models such as BPMN or PROV-O focus on process execution or provenance tracking, they lack the deep alignment with cultural heritage semantics required for safeguarding intangible heritage. Basing the craft modelling in CIDOC CRM enables compatibility with existing cultural heritage infrastructures and retains the flexibility to extend the model with domain-specific classes for crafts.

Crafting Actions and Events. In craft processes, individual actions are modelled as instances of 'E7 Activity', which is a subclass of the encompassing 'E5 Event'. E5 Event is the foundational category for any phenomenon with a discernible beginning and end in time. The 'E7 Activity' class refines for deliberate interventions executed by human agents, acting individually or collectively, to instigate a transformation in a material object or achieve a defined outcome.

These activities encompass the operational steps that constitute a craft process. Examples of such steps include shaping raw materials, joining separate components, applying decorative elements, or refining a material.

Each activity within a process does not occur in isolation. It is situated within a spatiotemporal context. To specify the temporal dimension of an activity, the E52 Time-Span class is employed. This class defines the time interval during which the action transpired. Location is captured through the E53 Place class, which enables the identification and recording of the physical environment where the action occurred. Spatiotemporal context provides a comprehensive understanding of the process, allowing for analysis and replication of the actions.

Agents. The individual or collective responsible for executing activities is represented as an instance of the 'E39 Actor' class. This categorisation is deliberately broad to encompass individuals and social groups that act in the crafting process. E39 is central to the agency and the involvement of practitioners. A single craftsman shaping a product, a team collaborating on a complex project, fall under the umbrella of the E39 Actor. Their involvement can range from direct manipulation and creation to oversight, decision-making, and the provision of necessary resources or support.

By modelling practitioners as Actors, we establish a link between the actor and the action. This allows for a comprehensive understanding of the production process, enabling tracking responsibilities, identifying stakeholders, and analysing the impact of human agency on the final result. This way, we provide a consistent framework for representing the roles of practitioners. Figure 1 presents the classes and relations used in our knowledge representation model.

Fig. 1. Knowledge Representation Classes and Relations.

Process Schemas. Execution of crafting actions is underpinned by the concept of a Process Schema, which is modelled as an instance of 'E29 Design or Procedure'. This classification situates Process Schemas under categories of E28 Conceptual Object and E90 Symbolic Object. These classes encompass the realm of non-physical entities, representing artefacts of thought, meaning, and codified knowledge.

An E29 Design or Procedure is defined as a specification detailing a course of action that is formulated to achieve an anticipated result. It does not describe or refer to a past or ongoing event; instead, it exists as a blueprint, a conceptual design, or a structured set of instructions that is interpreted and enacted by an agent. Figure 2 illustrates the KG structure of a craft Process Schema.

Fig. 2. Knowledge Graph Structure of a Craft Process Schema

We stress the distinction between the Process Schema and the concrete E7 Activity that it informs and directs. An Activity denotes an actual, situated event that unfolds in time and space, invariably involving some physical change. In contrast, an E29 Design or Procedure is a model of such events, existing in the realm of abstract concepts, providing a template for potential actions.

3.3 Knowledge Representation

Each step is associated with at least a set of action execution parameters and its action outcome. The parameters are the numerical values required to represent the action physically and are the same as those simulated in the FEA. They represent physical

quantities pertinent to environmental conditions and practitioner actions, such as temperature, gripping tool posture, and induced motion for tools. The state of affected entities during the action is computed in the simulation. In this way, an ostensive representation of actions and their results is achieved.

The presentation of action outcomes is not limited to the exemplary performance of the action. They contain alternative workflows per the outcomes of branching nodes. Common mistakes, e.g. incorrect tool angles or inappropriate material or condition choices, are also represented as diverging paths. These branches terminate in either recovery paths, showing how the mistake can be corrected, or in failure nodes, used to indicate irreversible outcomes. This enables the system to offer predictive guidance and real-time feedback during the simulation.

Craft knowledge encoded in the graph is multimodal. Each action node is linked to exemplars, including video recordings, verbal descriptions, and semantic annotations. These links facilitate a comprehensive and media-rich learning experience, allowing learners to review expert demonstrations in tandem with procedural simulation. A multilingual and hierarchically structured thesaurus ensures semantic consistency and interoperability across linguistic and cultural contexts.

This procedural, material, and contextual organisation of knowledge enables dynamic simulation scenarios that adapt to learner behaviour while preserving the epistemic integrity of traditional craft practices.

3.4 Education

The Craeft eLearning Portal serves as the central access point for all Craeft users, functioning as a comprehensive e-learning platform. It provides a wide array of functionalities designed to support and guide individuals through their craft education journey. The Craeft eLearning platform provided training courses required to master a particular craft.

Courses can be either educational, focusing on theoretical knowledge, or training, providing practical skills through hands-on practice. Lessons can be either online or offline and draw from diverse training materials, craft demonstrations, action visualisations, and action simulations. Course authoring involves linking these sources to lessons, as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. A course page is generated from the process schema representation.

FEM provides simulations based that are initialised using the process schema. The primary objective of these simulations is to visually represent the effects of applied forces and material transformations given a specific set of parameters. The simulator takes two key inputs: the parameters for the simulation and the simulation setup, which is derived directly from the process schema. The simulation results are a collection of object state sequences. These sequences represent the transformation of 3D objects as the virtual action is executed.

An application called 'Craft Studio' is the environment for rendering simulator outputs and is a suite of tools for authoring immersive educational and training materials. The Craft Studio is an interactive authoring application implemented in Unity. It provides features for authoring and executing both interactive simulations. The Craft Studio renders the simulation outputs within the Unity game engine.

The process schema is converted to a simulator input. A lesson is compiled into a Lesson Specification File, in JSON format, which is exported and uploaded to the eLearning portal. The theoretical components of the lesson are authored directly within the e-learning portal, containing all necessary material except for the execution aspects. This includes details such as tools, materials, and transformation mechanisms, all designed to appropriately introduce students to the lesson. The execution file for the lesson is the one previously uploaded from the Craft Studio and is linked as a resource within the lesson. Subsequently, the lesson is assigned to apprentices. Apprentices then download the Lesson Specification File and load it into the Apprentice Studio to undertake the lesson.

Workshops, tools, and machines are derived from the KG for craft or processes. The Craft Studio provides a graphical user interface (GUI) for authoring these lessons,

making use of these digital assets and renderers. Lesson scenarios are set within a virtual workshop environment. Authoring a Lesson scenario also includes defining its input/output interfaces. Student inputs come from the keyboard, mouse, and haptic devices. System outputs are delivered in 2D, 3D, XR (Extended Reality), and haptic rendering.

3.5 Real-Time FEM Interactive Simulation

The real-time simulation of manipulating deformable objects uses the NVIDIA PhysX simulator [21]. NVIDIA PhysX simulates complex physics interactions, including soft body dynamics, by leveraging the parallel processing capabilities of GPUs. The FEM is used to handle the complexities of soft body dynamics, ensuring that interactions between objects and the environment are faithfully represented. To achieve this, the objects are assigned properties such as elasticity, friction, and mass distribution. Given that the focus is on real-time applications, the set of physical properties is kept small. In the scenarios considered in this paper, the main external force is the one applied by the tool on the object that is manipulated.

We implemented the simulator using the PhysX SDK directly to build a module that gives full control over the performed manipulations. The developed module takes as input the physical properties, geometries, and initial states of the objects and outputs the deformed geometries. Physical properties and initial states of the actors are defined in configuration files. Different sets of parameters are defined for the soft bodies (materials that are manipulated) and rigid bodies (tools). Object geometry is imported using the Wavefront file format. The deformed meshes that result from the manipulations are passed to the subsequent rendering module for interactive visualisation. Figure 4 presents the interaction loop of the FEM simulator, highlighting the data flow between the simulation and rendering modules.

Fig. 4. An illustration showing the interaction loop of the FEM simulator.

The parameters of the simulation are recorded in JSON format and are acquired by the simulation engine during execution. To support interactive real-time simulations of crafting actions, the simulation core has been exported in the form of a DLL library. A Unity3D application has been developed that sets up the simulation environment within a Unity3D scene, and through the DLL, all the components of the

scene become available for manipulation via the Unity3D interfaces and through the creation of Unity3D script files. Based on this infrastructure standard, manipulators are integrated for controlling the rotation and translation of the tool. This allows support for repetitive practising of actions and incremental action flows.

Presently, process schemas are translated into simulator input through an intermediate JSON specification. A natural extension is to enable the simulation engine to consume semantic descriptions directly from the knowledge graph at runtime. This would allow the dynamic update according to modifications in the semantic representation, such as for newly added actions or new workflows. This technical integration ensures closer synchronisation between documentation and simulation. We envisage a future pipeline where semantic updates authored in the knowledge graph automatically propagate to the simulation environment, thereby reducing authoring overhead and strengthening the fidelity of training scenarios.

3.6 Physically Based Rendering for Result Visualisation

To reinforce its educational value, the system integrates physically based rendering (PBR) techniques that realistically visualise the workpiece after each interaction. Our rendering module employs light transport simulation informed by the output of the FEM engine, which encodes the material deformation and surface evolution resulting from the learner's actions.

Following the approach detailed in [18], we simulate optical phenomena such as subsurface scattering, refraction, and anisotropic reflection, critical for rendering complex craft materials such as polished wood, metal, glass, and ceramic. These effects reveal surface quality and underlying structure and, thus, carry instructional relevance. The renderer operates on material models parameterised by measurable physical attributes (e.g., roughness, metallicity, index of refraction), enabling meaningful variation in appearance corresponding to process outcomes.

Rendering is performed on mesh outputs derived from FEM-simulated deformation. In our pipeline, the FEM displacement field is used to morph the base mesh, preserving topological fidelity while enabling realistic damage, warping, or compression effects to be visualised. These mesh modifications are shaded using a physically based bidirectional scattering distribution function.

Photorealistic rendering aids immersion and visual appraisal. Learners interpret visual cues as indicators of procedural issues. This feedback links perception and reasoning, fostering understanding of cause-and-effect in craft.

4. Use Case and Evaluation

To demonstrate the proposed method, we consider a use case focused on carving wood and aluminium blocks. This scenario demonstrates how cylindrical and various chisels can be used to manipulate materials. The simulation provides real-time feedback on tool interaction, showing physical effects on blocks via physically based rendering. This use case integrates KGs, interactive FEM, and high-fidelity visualization for craft education.

4.1 Simulation setup

The PhysX scenes contain objects called actors. Each actor has a physical state and properties that include position, orientation, etc. Actor states evolve due to applied forces and interactions. In our case, two actors are defined at each time step of the simulation: the tool as a rigid body actor and the manipulated material as a soft body actor. Given the actor properties and initial states from the previous section, the simulation is straightforward using the appropriate PhysX SDK API calls.

4.2 Results

For the simulations, we used two types of materials: wood and aluminium. The duration was standardised (5 sec) to maintain consistency across experiments. Each scenario involved a tool, either a cylindrical or chisel type, interacting with one of the materials. The initial state of the objects includes their pose in 3D (translation, rotation), and their initial velocities. The tools were driven only by predetermined initial velocities to ensure repeatability and comparability of the results. These initial velocities were chosen to simulate realistic crafting actions. The properties of wood and aluminium were set according to typical physical characteristics of each material within the PhysX simulation environment, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Material properties in PhysX Simulations.

Material Property	Timber	Aluminium
Density (mass/volume)	650	2700.0
Dynamic Friction (dimensionless)	0.25	0.25
Young's Modulus (force/area)	$5 \cdot 10^9$	$70 \cdot 10^9$
Poisson's Ratio (dimensionless)	0.499	0.499
Elasticity Damping (dimensionless)	1.0	1.0
Damping Scale (dimensionless)	1.0	1.0

Simulation results, shown in Figures 5-6, demonstrate high realism for materials like wood and aluminium under cylindrical and chisel tools. Plastic deformation for wood material is not calculated due to the increased processing cost. Different incidence forces and angles caused distinct deformations in each material, highlighting material-specific responses. The simulations accurately model tool-material interactions, providing visual fidelity for realistic craft education.

5. Discussion and Future Work

This framework combines KGs, interactive FEM simulation, and high-fidelity visualization to create an effective learning environment for traditional crafts. It allows learners to practice procedurally, receiving feedback based on authentic domain knowledge. A key benefit is the externalisation of tacit knowledge, structuring craft procedures as ontologically grounded KGs, which supports modular,

multilingual, and semantically interoperable representations of craft actions. This enables systematic training workflows and safeguards endangered crafts.

Fig. 5. Simulation of the effect of cylindrical tools on aluminium and wood surfaces. Each row shows exemplar frames from three simulations. Different contact forces and angles are simulated, showcasing the different impacts on the deformation of the surface.

Fig. 6. Simulation of the effect of chisel tools on a wooden surface. Each row shows frames from different simulations. Different contact forces and angles are simulated.

Fig. 7. Manipulation of the tools in 3D.

The simulation environment provides a safe and cost-effective space for experiential learning. Learners may practice complex procedures without the risks associated with material waste or tool misuse. Real-time FEM feedback enhances procedural understanding, while photorealistic rendering of outcomes supports visual assessment and reflection on one's actions. Exemplars and decision modelling within the KG reinforce understanding through situated comparison and error recovery.

Some limitations remain. The current system is optimised for well-defined procedural sequences with observable outcomes. More complex craft processes involving subjective decision-making, fine-motor precision, or ambiguous success criteria may require additional modelling strategies. The accurate simulation of certain materials, particularly fibrous, layered, or porous substances, remains a technical challenge in FEM and rendering. Future work will expand the system's applicability by extending the ontology to new craft domains (e.g., fibre arts, leatherworking). We plan to integrate haptic feedback and motion capture for enhanced realism. User studies will evaluate pedagogical impact, focusing on error awareness, procedural retention, and cross-domain knowledge sharing.

This work is part of the Horizon Europe project Craeft, which brings together computer scientists, heritage experts, and craft practitioners in a coordinated effort to safeguard and transmit traditional craftsmanship in Europe. Within Craeft, the proposed approach documents craft processes in semantically interoperable formats, building knowledge bases enriched with multimodal resources, and enabling innovative learning environments for practitioners and apprentices. By integrating knowledge graphs, FEM-based simulation, and physically based rendering, this work complements project activities such as motion capture benchmarks, multimodal craft dictionaries, and online repositories of craft knowledge.

Acknowledgements: This research was funded by the European Commission in the context of the Horizon Europe research and innovation program in the project Craeft, 101094349.

References

1. Abu-Salih, B., Alotaibi, S.: A systematic literature review of knowledge graph construction and application in education. *Heliyon*. 10, e25383 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e25383>.
2. Weichselbraun, A., Waldvogel, R., Fraefel, A., Van Schie, A., Kuntschik, P.: Building Knowledge Graphs and Recommender Systems for Suggesting Reskilling and Upskilling Options from the Web. *Information*. 13, 510 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.3390/info13110510>.
3. Fan, X., Sun, Y., Wang, Q., Wang, X.: Research on the Application of Knowledge Graph in Higher Education of Art and Design. In: Kaki, S., Majoul, B., Mohd Sharif, M.F., and Syed Mohammed, S.F. (eds.) *Proceedings of the 2024 6th International Conference on Literature, Art and Human Development (ICLAHD 2024)*. pp. 494–501. Atlantis Press SARL, Paris (2024). https://doi.org/10.2991/978-2-38476-319-1_57.
4. Osterloh, M., Frey, B.S.: Motivation, Knowledge Transfer, and Organizational Forms. *Organ. Sci.* 11, 538–550 (2000). <https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.11.5.538.15204>.
5. Zabolis, X., Partarakis, N., Demeridou, I., Doulgeraki, P., Zidianakis, E., Argyros, A., Theodoridou, M., Marketakis, Y., Meghini, C., Bartalesi, V., Pratelli, N., Holz, C., Strelis, P., Meier, M., Seidler, M.K., Werup, L., Sichani, P.F., Manitsaris, S., Senteri, G., Dubois, A., Ringas, C., Ziouva, A., Tasiopoulou, E., Kaplanidi, D., Arnaud, D., Hee, P., Canavate, G., Benvenuti, M.-A., Krivokapic, J.: A Roadmap for Craft Understanding, Education,

- Training, and Preservation. *Heritage*. 6, 5305–5328 (2023).
<https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage6070280>.
6. Zabulis, X., Meghini, C., Dubois, A., Doulgeraki, P., Partarakis, N., Adami, I., Karuzaki, E., Carre, A.-L., Patsiouras, N., Kaplanidi, D., Metilli, D., Bartalesi, V., Ringas, C., Tasiopoulou, E., Stefanidi, Z.: Digitisation of Traditional Craft Processes. *J. Comput. Cult. Herit.* 15, 1–24 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3494675>.
 7. Zabulis, X., Partarakis, N., Bartalesi, V., Pratelli, N., Meghini, C., Dubois, A., Moreno, I., Manitsaris, S.: Multimodal Dictionaries for Traditional Craft Education. *Multimodal Technol. Interact.* 8, 63 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.3390/mti8070063>.
 8. Partarakis, N., Zabulis, X.: Applying Cognitive Load Theory to eLearning of Crafts. *Multimodal Technol. Interact.* 8, 2 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3390/mti8010002>.
 9. Olivas-Padilla, B.E., Glushkova, A., Manitsaris, S.: Motion Capture Benchmark of Real Industrial Tasks and Traditional Crafts for Human Movement Analysis. *IEEE Access*. 11, 40075–40092 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3269581>.
 10. Knudson, M.M., Khaw, L., Bullard, M.K., Dicker, R., Cohen, M.J., Staudenmayer, K., Sadjadi, J., Howard, S., Gaba, D., Krummel, T.: Trauma Training in Simulation: Translating Skills From SIM Time to Real Time. *J. Trauma Inj. Infect. Crit. Care*. 64, 255–264 (2008). <https://doi.org/10.1097/TA.0b013e31816275b0>.
 11. Menghal, P.M., Laxmi, A.J.: Real time simulation: A novel approach in engineering education. In: 2011 3rd International Conference on Electronics Computer Technology. pp. 215–219. IEEE, Kanyakumari, India (2011).
<https://doi.org/10.1109/ICECTECH.2011.5941592>.
 12. Chambers, T.L., Aglawe, A., Reiners, D., White, S., Borst, C.W., Prachyabrued, M., Bajpayee, A.: Real-time simulation for a virtual reality-based MIG welding training system. *Virtual Real.* 16, 45–55 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10055-010-0170-x>.
 13. Lee, Y., Ko, C., Lee, H., Jeon, K., Shin, S., Han, C.: Interactive plant simulation modeling for developing an operator training system in a natural gas pressure-regulating station. *Pet. Sci.* 14, 529–538 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12182-017-0170-5>.
 14. Vergnano, A., Berselli, G., Pellicciari, M.: Interactive simulation-based-training tools for manufacturing systems operators: an industrial case study. *Int. J. Interact. Des. Manuf. IJIDeM*. 11, 785–797 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12008-016-0367-7>.
 15. Tang, L., Cao, Y., Liu, Z., Qian, K., Liu, Y., Liu, Y., Zhou, Y.: Improving the quality of preclinical simulation training for dental students using a new digital real-time evaluation system. *Eur. J. Dent. Educ.* 25, 100–107 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1111/eje.12580>.
 16. Antonovsky, A., Pollock, C., Straker, L.: Identification of the Human Factors Contributing to Maintenance Failures in a Petroleum Operation. *Hum. Factors J. Hum. Factors Ergon. Soc.* 56, 306–321 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018720813491424>.
 17. Wolff, R., Preusche, C., Gerndt, A.: A modular architecture for an interactive real-time simulation and training environment for satellite on-orbit servicing. *J. Simul.* 8, 50–63 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1057/jos.2013.10>.
 18. Zabulis, X., Partarakis, N., Demeridou, I., Bartalesi, V., Pratelli, N., Meghini, C., Nikolaou, N., Fallahian, P.: Modelling and Simulation of Traditional Craft Actions. *Appl. Sci.* 14, 7750 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.3390/app14177750>.
 19. Zabulis, X., Stamou, A., Demeridou, I., Koutlemanis, P., Karamaounas, P., Papageridis, V., Partarakis, N.: Simulation and Visualisation of Traditional Craft Actions. *Heritage*. 7, 7083–7114 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage7120328>.
 20. Xu, R., Xu, J.: Research on Interactive Traditional Craft Diagram Model and Simulation System: Take Nanjing Rong Hua Craft as an Example. In: Proceedings of the 2016 2nd International Conference on Advances in Energy, Environment and Chemical Engineering (AEECE 2016). Atlantis Press, Singapore (2016).
<https://doi.org/10.2991/aece-16.2016.54>.
 21. NVIDIA: PhysX, <https://github.com/NVIDIA-Omniverse/PhysX>, (2024).